

RICE IMPORT RESTRICTION POLICY AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM THE SOUTH-EAST REGION

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of rice import restriction policy on rice production in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Despite the introduction of trade restrictions aimed at promoting domestic production, their effectiveness remains uncertain, particularly at the regional level. Using primary data collected from 400 smallholder rice farmers across Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States, the study employs descriptive statistics and an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model to analyze the relationship between policy intervention and production outcomes. The results show that, although farmers perceive the policy as beneficial, the rice import restriction policy does not have a statistically significant effect on rice production. Similarly, access to inputs, technology use, market conditions, and infrastructure are not significant determinants of production. The model exhibits low explanatory power, indicating that rice production is driven by broader structural and institutional factors not captured in the analysis. The study concludes that trade restriction policies alone are insufficient to drive sustainable agricultural productivity. It emphasizes the need for an integrated policy approach that combines trade measures with investments in inputs, infrastructure, technology, and institutional capacity. The findings contribute to the policy debate by providing region-specific empirical evidence from the South-East and highlighting the importance of addressing structural constraints to achieve food security in Nigeria.

Keywords: Rice import restriction policy; agricultural productivity; OLS regression; smallholder farmers; Nigeria; food security

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1 Introduction

Rice is one of the most important staple foods in Nigeria, with rapidly growing demand driven by population growth, urbanization, and changing consumption patterns. Despite significant domestic production, the country continues to face a substantial gap between rice demand and supply, leading to reliance on imports and exposure to global price fluctuations.

In response, the Nigerian government introduced a rice import restriction policy in 2015, combining high tariffs and foreign exchange controls to encourage domestic production. While the policy has been widely promoted as a strategy for achieving food self-sufficiency, its effectiveness remains contested, particularly at the regional level.

Existing empirical studies, such as Jacob (2024) and Esheya (2024), report that rice import restriction policies have contributed to modest increases in domestic rice production in Nigeria. However, these gains are uneven across regions and are constrained by underlying structural limitations. Similarly, Nwachukwu and Achike (2020) highlight persistent challenges, including limited access to improved inputs, credit facilities, and mechanization services.

Institutional evidence from the Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (2021) further indicates that inefficiencies within the agricultural value chain, coupled with infrastructural deficits, continue to limit productivity gains. Despite these insights, there is limited empirical evidence on the effectiveness of rice import restriction policies at the regional level, particularly in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria.

This study addresses this gap by examining the impact of rice import restriction policy on rice production in South-East Nigeria using econometric analysis. Specifically, it evaluates whether policy interventions and key structural factors significantly influence production outcomes among smallholder farmers.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical framework and empirical literature, Section 3 describes the methodology, Section 4 discusses the empirical results, and Section 5 concludes with policy implications.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in agricultural production theory and trade theory, particularly the concept of protectionism. Agricultural production theory explains output as a function of key inputs such as land, labor, capital, and technology (Nicholson & Snyder, 2017; Varian, 2019). In this study, rice production depends on farmers' access to inputs, adoption of technology, availability of infrastructure, and prevailing market conditions. Accordingly, rice production is specified as a function of key explanatory variables, including input access (INPUT), technology use (TECH), market conditions (MARKET), and infrastructure (INFRA).

Trade theory, particularly the principle of protectionism, provides the basis for understanding the role of import restriction policies. It argues that restricting imports through tariffs or quotas can protect domestic industries from foreign competition and stimulate local production (Krugman, Obstfeld, & Melitz, 2018). In Nigeria, the rice import restriction policy was introduced to reduce dependence on imports and promote domestic rice production. However, the effectiveness of such policies depends on the presence of complementary factors. Protectionist measures alone may not increase productivity if domestic producers face structural constraints such as limited access to inputs, inadequate infrastructure, and weak institutional support.

The integration of these theoretical perspectives provides a framework for analyzing the relationship between rice import restriction policy and agricultural productivity. While trade policy may create incentives for increased production, actual output depends on the availability and efficient use of production factors. This theoretical linkage underpins the empirical model specified in this study, where rice production is modeled as a function of policy and structural variables.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

The relationship between trade policy and agricultural productivity has been widely examined in the literature. Studies such as Jacob (2024) and Esheya (2024) report that import restriction policies can stimulate domestic production by protecting local farmers from foreign competition. However, these effects are often conditional on the availability of complementary inputs and supportive infrastructure.

Nwachukwu and Achike (2020) highlight that limited access to improved seeds, fertilizers, credit, and mechanization remains a major constraint to agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Similarly, institutional evidence from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2023) shows that high production costs and inefficiencies within the agricultural value chain constrain the effectiveness of policy interventions.

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2021) emphasizes that structural constraints; including poor infrastructure, post-harvest losses, and weak institutions, significantly limit agricultural productivity in developing countries. Data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023) also indicate persistent increases in rice prices despite policy interventions, suggesting that domestic production growth has not kept pace with demand.

Overall, the literature shows that while trade restrictions can provide incentives for local production, their effectiveness depends on broader structural and institutional conditions.

Despite this growing body of research, several gaps remain. Existing empirical studies (Jacob, 2024; Esheya, 2024) largely focus on national-level outcomes and report modest increases in domestic rice production. However, they often overlook regional variations in policy effectiveness, particularly in the South-East geopolitical zone.

Furthermore, although previous studies (Nwachukwu & Achike, 2020) identify structural constraints such as limited access to inputs, credit, and mechanization, there is limited empirical evidence that integrates these factors into a unified econometric framework to assess their combined effects on rice production. Institutional reports from the Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (2021) also highlight persistent inefficiencies in the agricultural value chain; however, these insights are rarely tested using micro-level data.

In addition, much of the existing literature relies on aggregate or secondary data, with limited use of primary farm-level data to capture farmers' actual production experiences and perceptions of policy impact. This creates a gap between macro-level policy analysis and micro-level production realities.

This study addresses these gaps by using primary data collected from smallholder rice farmers in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States and applying an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression framework to examine the combined effects of rice import restriction policy and key structural factors on rice production. In doing so, the study provides region-specific evidence and contributes to a more nuanced understanding of trade policy effectiveness in Nigeria's agricultural sector.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection and Sampling

This study utilizes primary data collected from 400 smallholder rice farmers across Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo States in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to ensure adequate representation across the study area, with proportional allocation based on the relative importance of rice production in each state.

3.2 Data Transformation and Variable Construction

Raw survey responses were transformed into quantitative variables suitable for econometric analysis. The coding process involved converting categorical responses into numerical values and constructing composite indices for multidimensional variables.

The dependent variable, rice production outcome (Y), was measured using an ordinal scale reflecting changes in production levels (1 = decrease, 2 = no change, 3 = increase). The policy variable, rice import restriction policy (PRIRP), was also coded as an ordinal variable capturing respondents' perceptions (1 = negative, 2 = neutral, 3 = positive).

Access to agricultural inputs (INPUT) was constructed as a composite index derived from multiple indicators, including access to improved seeds, fertilizer, mechanization, and irrigation. Each component was coded as a binary variable (1 = access, 0 = no access), and the index was computed as the average of these components, resulting in a normalized scale ranging from 0 to 1.

Technology use (TECH) was proxied by access to mechanization services and treated as a binary variable (1 = yes, 0 = no). Market conditions (MARKET) were measured by access to markets for selling produce and coded as a binary variable. Infrastructure (INFRA) was constructed as an index based on indicators such as road access and storage facilities and normalized on a 0–1 scale.

This transformation process ensures consistency between the questionnaire design, variable measurement, and econometric modeling, thereby improving the reliability and validity of the analysis.

3.3 Model Specifications

The study employs an OLS regression model to examine the relationship between rice production and selected explanatory variables.

The functional form of the model is as follows:

$$Y = f(PRIRP, INPUT, TECH, MARKET, INFRA)$$

The explicit model is specified as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PRIRP + \beta_2 INPUT + \beta_3 TECH + \beta_4 MARKET + \beta_5 INFRA + \mu$$

Where:

Y = Rice production outcome

PRIRP = Perception of rice import restriction policy

INPUT = Access to agricultural inputs

TECH = Technology use

MARKET = Market conditions

INFRA = Infrastructure

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 – β_5 = Parameters

μ = Error term

3.4 Estimation Technique

The study employs the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique due to its efficiency and ability to provide unbiased parameter estimates under the classical linear regression assumptions. Prior to estimation, the dataset was screened and cleaned to ensure completeness and consistency. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the data, while correlation analysis was conducted to examine relationships among the variables.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables Used in the Model

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Y (Rice Production)	2.53	0.708	1	3
PRIRP (Policy)	2.25	0.767	1	3
INFRA (Infrastructure)	0.38	0.341	0	1
TECH (Technology)	0.4	0.491	0	1
MARKET (Market Conditions)	0.43	0.495	0	1
INPUT (Access to Inputs)	0.44	0.252	0	1

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The descriptive statistics of the variables used in the analysis are presented in Table 1. The results reflect the transformed and coded dataset derived from the survey responses. The dependent variable, rice production outcome (Y), has a mean value of 2.53, indicating that respondents reported an overall increase in production following the implementation of the rice import restriction policy. Since Y is measured on an ordinal scale (1 = decrease, 2 = no change, 3 = increase), this reflects a generally positive production trend among farmers.

The policy variable (PRIRP) has a mean value of 2.25, indicating that respondents generally perceive the rice import restriction policy as positive. The standard deviation shows some variation in these perceptions across respondents.

Access to agricultural inputs (INPUT), measured as a composite index ranging from 0 to 1, has a mean value of 0.44, indicating moderate but insufficient access to critical production inputs such as improved seeds, fertilizer, mechanization, and irrigation. Technology use (TECH = 0.40) shows that approximately 40% of respondents utilize mechanization services, reflecting low adoption of modern production technologies.

Similarly, market access (MARKET = 0.43) indicates that less than half of the farmers have reliable access to markets for selling their produce. Infrastructure (INFRA), also measured as an index, has a mean value of 0.38, highlighting significant infrastructural constraints within the study area.

Overall, the standard deviation values indicate moderate variability across the variables, suggesting that the dataset is suitable for econometric estimation.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of Variables

Variable	Y	PRIRP	INFRA	TECH	MARKET	INPUT
Y	1	-0.072	0.013	-0.022	-0.009	-0.006
PRIRP	-0.072	1	0.101	0.02	0.102	0.105
INFRA	0.013	0.101	1	0.713	0.063	0.684
TECH	-0.022	0.02	0.713	1	0.041	0.491
MARKET	-0.009	0.102	0.063	0.041	1	0.021
INPUT	-0.006	0.105	0.684	0.491	0.021	1

Source: Author’s computation (2026)

The correlation matrix in Table 2 shows generally weak linear relationships between rice production and the explanatory variables. The correlation between rice production (Y) and the policy variable (PRIRP) is weak and negative, indicating that positive perceptions of the policy do not correspond to higher production outcomes.

Similarly, INPUT, TECH, MARKET, and INFRA exhibit weak correlations with rice production, indicating that variations in these variables are not strongly associated with changes in production levels.

However, a relatively strong positive correlation is observed between infrastructure (INFRA) and technology use (TECH), indicating that better infrastructure is associated with greater adoption of mechanization. Despite this relationship, these variables do not have a statistically significant effect in the regression results.

4.3 Regression Results

Table 3: OLS Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Probability
Constant	2.686	0.124	21.701	0
PRIRP (Policy)	-0.07	0.047	-1.497	0.135
INFRA (Infrastructure)	0.181	0.178	1.013	0.312
TECH (Technology)	-0.102	0.103	-0.987	0.324
MARKET (Market Conditions)	-0.005	0.072	-0.064	0.949

INPUT (Access to Inputs)	-0.064	0.193	-0.33	0.742
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Source: Author's computation (2026)

Table 3 presents the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression results, while Appendix A provides the detailed SPSS output. The findings show that none of the explanatory variables; rice import restriction policy (PRIRP), access to inputs (INPUT), technology use (TECH), market conditions (MARKET), and infrastructure (INFRA), are statistically significant at conventional levels. The coefficient of the policy variable (RIRP) is negative and statistically insignificant, indicating that the rice import restriction policy does not have a measurable effect on rice production within the study area.

Similarly, INPUT, TECH, MARKET, and INFRA all exhibit statistically insignificant coefficients, indicating that variations in these factors do not explain differences in rice production among respondents.

The model's explanatory power is very low, as reflected by the R^2 value, which indicates that the included variables account for only a small proportion of the variation in rice production. This suggests that other unobserved factors, such as climatic conditions, soil quality, farm management practices, and institutional constraints, play a more important role in determining production outcomes.

4.4 Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between rice import restriction policy and agricultural productivity in the South-East region of Nigeria. When interpreted in light of the theoretical and empirical literature, several key implications emerge.

From a theoretical perspective, the results challenge the expectations of trade theory, particularly the principle of protectionism, which argues that restricting imports should stimulate domestic production by shielding local producers from foreign competition. Although farmers in the study area perceive the rice import restriction policy positively, the econometric results show that the policy does not have a statistically significant effect on rice production. This indicates that the assumptions of protectionist trade theory may not hold in contexts where complementary production factors are weak or inadequate.

However, the findings are consistent with agricultural production theory, which posits that output depends on the availability and efficiency of key inputs such as land, labor, capital, and technology. The insignificance of INPUT, TECH, MARKET, and INFRA suggests that these production factors are either insufficient or not effectively utilized. This supports the argument that policy incentives alone cannot improve productivity without strengthening the underlying production environment.

Empirically, the results align with previous studies, such as Jacob (2024) and Esheya (2024), which show that structural constraints often limit the impact of import restriction policies. Similarly, the findings reinforce the conclusions of Nwachukwu and Achike (2020), who highlight persistent challenges related to input access, credit, and mechanization.

Institutional evidence further supports these findings. Reports from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2023) show that high production costs and inefficiencies within the value chain constrain policy effectiveness in the agricultural sector. Likewise, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO, 2021) emphasizes that infrastructural deficits, post-harvest losses, and institutional weaknesses significantly limit productivity in developing economies. These factors help explain the low explanatory power of the model and the insignificance of the explanatory variables.

In addition, the weak relationships observed in the correlation analysis, together with the very low explanatory power of the model ($R^2 = 0.008$), indicate that rice production is influenced by a broader set of factors not captured in the model, including environmental conditions, farm management practices, and institutional quality. This highlights a key limitation of relying solely on policy-driven approaches to agricultural development.

Overall, the findings confirm the central argument of the theoretical framework: while trade policy may create incentives for domestic production, actual productivity outcomes depend on the availability and effective use of complementary inputs and institutional support. The results also reinforce the empirical consensus that rice import restriction policies in Nigeria have produced partial and uneven outcomes, particularly in regions with significant structural constraints.

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of rice import restriction policy on rice production in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria using primary data and an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression framework. The findings show that, although farmers perceive the policy as beneficial, the rice import restriction policy does not have a statistically significant effect on rice production. Similarly, access to inputs, technology use, market conditions, and infrastructure are not significant determinants of production within the study area.

These results indicate that trade restriction policies alone are insufficient to drive sustainable agricultural productivity. While such policies may create incentives for domestic production, their effectiveness is constrained by structural and institutional challenges, including limited access to inputs, inadequate infrastructure, weak market systems, and low adoption of modern technologies.

The study concludes that achieving meaningful improvements in rice production in Nigeria requires a comprehensive and integrated policy approach that goes beyond import restrictions. Strengthening the agricultural production environment through improved input delivery systems, enhanced infrastructure, effective extension services, and better market coordination is essential for translating policy incentives into tangible productivity gains.

Overall, the findings contribute to the policy debate by providing region-specific empirical evidence from the South-East and highlighting the need to align trade policy with broader agricultural development strategies to achieve sustainable food security outcomes.

5.2 Policy Implications

The findings of this study have important implications for agricultural policy design and implementation in Nigeria. First, the absence of a statistically significant relationship between rice import restriction policy and rice production indicates that trade protection measures alone are insufficient to drive sustainable agricultural productivity. Policymakers should therefore reconsider the heavy reliance on import restrictions as a primary strategy for achieving food self-sufficiency.

Second, the insignificance of key structural variables; including access to inputs, technology use, market conditions, and infrastructure, indicates that existing interventions in these areas are inadequate, poorly targeted, or inefficiently implemented. This highlights the need to shift from policy formulation to effective policy execution, particularly by improving input delivery systems, strengthening extension services, and ensuring that investments in infrastructure translate into tangible benefits for farmers.

Third, the divergence between farmers' positive perceptions of the policy and its lack of measurable impact on production underscores the importance of evidence-based policymaking. While perception-driven support may enhance political acceptability, it does not guarantee productivity gains. Policymakers should therefore prioritize monitoring and evaluation frameworks that focus on measurable outcomes rather than perceived benefits.

Furthermore, the low explanatory power of the model indicates that rice production is influenced by broader structural and environmental factors not fully captured in current policy frameworks. This suggests that agricultural policy should adopt a more integrated approach that incorporates climate variability, farm-level management practices, access to credit, and institutional capacity into policy design.

Overall, the findings reinforce the need for a holistic and coordinated agricultural policy framework that aligns trade policy with investments in production factors and institutional systems. Without addressing these

underlying structural constraints, the effectiveness of rice import restriction policies in achieving sustainable agricultural productivity will remain limited.

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APPENDIX A: SPSS REGRESSION OUTPUT

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Y	2.53	.708	400
PRIRP	2.25	.767	400
INFRA	.375	.3405	400
TECH	.40	.491	400
MARKET	.43	.495	400
INPUT	.4438	.25211	400

Correlations

		Y	PRIRP	INFRA	TECH	MARKET	INPUT
Pearson Correlation	Y	1.000	-.072	.013	-.022	-.009	-.006
	PRIRP	-.072	1.000	.101	.020	.102	.105
	INFRA	.013	.101	1.000	.713	.063	.684
	TECH	-.022	.020	.713	1.000	.041	.491
	MARKET	-.009	.102	.063	.041	1.000	.021
	INPUT	-.006	.105	.684	.491	.021	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Y	.	.077	.398	.333	.429	.451
	PRIRP	.077	.	.022	.345	.020	.018
	INFRA	.398	.022	.	.000	.104	.000
	TECH	.333	.345	.000	.	.205	.000
	MARKET	.429	.020	.104	.205	.	.335
	INPUT	.451	.018	.000	.000	.335	.
N	Y	400	400	400	400	400	400
	PRIRP	400	400	400	400	400	400
	INFRA	400	400	400	400	400	400
	TECH	400	400	400	400	400	400
	MARKET	400	400	400	400	400	400
	INPUT	400	400	400	400	400	400

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.091 ^a	.008	-.004	.709

a. Predictors: (Constant), INPUT, MARKET, PRIRP, TECH, INFRA**ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.654	5	.331	.658	.656 ^b
	Residual	198.096	394	.503		
	Total	199.750	399			

a. Dependent Variable: Y**b. Predictors: (Constant), INPUT, MARKET, PRIRP, TECH, INFRA****Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.686	.124		21.701	.000
	PRIRP	-.070	.047	-.076	-1.497	.135
	INFRA	.181	.178	.087	1.013	.312
	TECH	-.102	.103	-.071	-.987	.324
	MARKET	-.005	.072	-.003	-.064	.949
	INPUT	-.064	.193	-.023	-.330	.742

a. Dependent Variable: Y